

Trip Report: Culvertown Platform Addendum

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Original Paper: <http://bit.ly/2Nu0W0m>

This paper best viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3gPWsPE>

Virtual tour: <https://cloud.3dvista.com/hosting/6964734/6/index.htm>

Video Tour: <https://youtu.be/J02zMNQOIyY>

Synopsis

A second trip to the platform was scheduled to provide some high definition drone photography of the platform. Secondly, to recheck the electromagnetics of the site. Finally to use the photography and digitally put the stones back together, and re-measure the equatorial: polar diameter ratios.

Unfortunately, the site has been tampered with, even since 2018, and many of the stones are now missing (compared with the before). Erosion appears to be a factor as well. But it seems likely that the site is too demolished to get a perfect DR measurement even with an orthogonal perspective. However, based on Figure 2, and utilizing the edges of the gray area/stone area, that there will be an approximate 65:55 ratio or 1.18. That is a 4.07% difference with the Ramesses II stele, as per the author's previous paper¹. However, the shape is different and is closer to the Cosmic Egg than an ellipse, or is very nearly triangular.

This means the site remains -and is growing due to destruction- a mystery (but the stones are natural).

¹ "The Solar Orb in Egypt", R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38492475/The_Solar_Orb_in_Egypt

Figures

Figure 1 - LiDAR scan

Figure 2 - Platform from orthogonal perspective, HD; credit: I. Cooper/Green Hat

Figure 3 - Closer perspective; credit: I. Cooper/Green Hat

Figure 4 - LiDAR of distance from platform to nearby knob; credit: KYFromAbove

Unique Issue

After getting the platform photographed, we asked Isaac, a certified Part 107 Drone photography professional, to send the drone to the nearby knob (see Figure 4). Reviews of my papers will recall that the Knobs of Kentucky are demonstrative of electrical formation, especially being giant lichtenburgs in the core region². This is not a core region and the knobs stand alone. So what follows was not an expected result, and we only sent the drone for reconnaissance and archeological reasons.

“We began flying on 06/19/21 around a rock structure located in New Haven! Equipped with my DJI Mavic Pro and three batteries we were prepared to do close to an hour and a half flight time. We covered the rock structure in New Haven with zero problems. However, on battery two we decided to go check out a peak near the sight. (sic)

The flight there was fine and it was a clear day so maintaining line of sight wasn't hard. It wasn't till I went to set my point of interest within the DJI app that I started to have problems. Setting a point of interest requires you to go to the center of the object you are trying to circle. As soon as I hovered above the center of that peak, nothing. By nothing I mean, I lost my camera, altitude data, and performance was heavily interfered with. I began navigating back with visual sight but, during this time my battery life was cut in half.

I have been flying drones legally since the age of 16 with a Part 107 License, and never within my time flying have I encountered problems like these without a known external factor. These factors can be a wide variety of things such as satellite signal, antenna interference, weather, gimbal errors, etc. Not the case this time though, in fact, we had great signal strength. I couldn't even record, pressing the record button would switch me into taking a photo and ultimately would time out!”

~Isaac Cooper

It's important to note that the drone was at an altitude of about 400'. This EM pulse could only have either been enormous, or part of a birkeland current connecting to the plasmasphere. There are no other structures, i.e. manmade, on that knob.

Footage of the approach @ <https://youtu.be/t4g6OvMjy18>

A Unique Iron Ore vein?

This piece caught the author's eye because it appears to defy uniformitarian formation principles. That does not prove electrical formation, however, it is rather unusual. The entire piece has aged the same amount of time, but it does not appear to be deforming at the same rate.

² See the “Plasmaglyphs and Megafauna Extinctions” paper, or other similar papers for examples or, just pull up the imagery for above the knobs region circa Hustonville, KY. Once seen, it cannot be unseen.

Figures 5 - 10: Iron ore vein; credit: R. Careaga

Note the unusual feature that if compressed near the “hinge” the other side widens (and indeed there was organic root material growing between, now dead). But if pressed there, the hinge separates. Gives the impression to the author that the piece formed quickly and not together. However, it fits very well together and probably was one piece in situ. But how can it then deform at different rates?

Conclusions

There are no new conclusions from this study, only more questions. Good science involves repeatable, testable hypotheses. The author is not clear that there are testable hypotheses in this case. There is some hope that in a few years, with trust we may convince the owner to allow us to dig a trench on the already partially destroyed end, from the road, and attempt to get beneath the plinths in order to discover if there is indeed another layer, because it seems like only dirt is beneath them. If this is the case then we’d suggest that it is a Megalithic Period structure, man made, probably as an observation deck. If however it is connected to more sandstone layers, then it would seem to suggest instead the mountaintop was removed to reveal the layer. There are no current plans to do this, and it would involve some logistics. But the owner seems to be as curious as we are. We will keep the readers informed.